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**KEY DIRECTIONS IN THE ORGANIZATION OF
HEALTH CARE AND PREVENTION ACTIONS TO
REDUCE MORTALITY FROM CARDIOVASCULAR
DISEASES IN UKRAINE**

Mishchenko M.,
M.D.

Kharkiv National Medical University

Shevchenko A.,

M.D., Master of Medicine, Economics and Pedagogy
Director of the Kharkiv Regional Institute of Public Health Services

Mishchenko A.

M.D., Ph.D., Assistant professor
Kharkiv Regional Institute of Public Health Services

Myocardial infarction and cerebral strokes are the main cause of death of Ukrainians [1; 2]. Annually in Ukraine, 40-50 thousand myocardial infarction and 100-150 thousand cerebral strokes happen. Mortality is 260-280 and 120-140 cases per 100 thousand of population per year, respectively [3; 4]. The organization of medical care for patients with acute myocardial infarction in Ukraine can be considered satisfactory (more than 40 specialized reperfusion centers; only 1 out of 7 victims of myocardial infarction die; therapy is less expensive; diagnosis is easier; cardiac surgeons and cardiologists can provide assistance), but the same cannot be said about the organization of medical care for patients with cerebral stroke (specialized unit stroke centers; mortality of 30-40% in the first 30 days, and up to 50% in the first year after a stroke; high disability identification; there is not enough diagnostic equipment and qualified medical personnel to provide assistance, thrombolysis is very expensive for Ukrainians; there are ten times fewer thrombolysis per thousand injured compared to countries in Western Europe; treatment is often carried out without observing clinical protocols; it is not necessary to enter data in the register of stroke patients [5]). In recent years, Ukraine has made progress in reducing mortality from myocardial infarction: in 11 regions in the hospital, it decreased by 20%. This is due to an increase in the number of coronary stentings, provision of clinics with angiographs and improvement of treatment protocols.

For the survival of patients with cerebral strokes, the most important is the proper organization of medical care provided within the "therapeutic window" (4.5 hours after the incident). The prehospital grading system is known to improve stroke care. In particular, the recently introduced Stockholm stroke screening system, which combines symptom severity and teleconsultation, leads to significantly faster patient delivery for endovascular thrombectomy and intravenous thrombolysis [6; 7]. In Ukraine, time for assistance is lost during the delivery of the victim to the clinic and

during the transfer of the victim between the clinics, one of which can carry out diagnostics, the second - treatment [8].

Medical care should be provided in specialized stroke departments or centers where an ambulance should deliver the patient with a diagnosis of stroke. Such stroke centers should be located a maximum of an hour from any settlement, taking into account the condition of the road surface and possible traffic jams. In Ukraine, the last two decades have indicated the need to create such centers, but only two full-fledged institutions have been created. The minimum financing of one case of cerebral stroke in the amount of 19.5 thousand UAH. at the expense of state funds, it has been carried out only since April of the current (2020) year, according to many experts it is insufficient, and it will still require a supplement from the victim's relatives at least in the amount of 40% of the total real cost of treatment [9].

In such conditions, the preventive direction remains relevant. WHO claims that 80% of premature heart attacks and strokes can be prevented by addressing risk factors such as tobacco use, unhealthy diets and obesity, lack of physical activity and harmful use of alcohol, using strategies that cover the entire population [10; 11]. The most manageable risk factor is tobacco smoking.

The effect of smoking on mortality from cardiovascular diseases is proved by the fact that with a decrease in the number of people who smoke, the number of cases of vascular accidents also decreases [12]. A similar trend is observed in all countries of the world [13]. In connection with this fact, Ukraine should strengthen the prevention of tobacco use, as well as not stop the health care reform related to the improvement of medical care protocols, state funding for the treatment of cardiovascular accidents, the creation of regional stroke centers with the provision of necessary equipment, materials and medicines for thrombolysis and thromectomy (thromboextractions), as well as by qualified medical personnel.

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